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MÉTHODES TRADITIONNELLES CONTRE MÉTHODE D'ENSEIGNEMENT DES LANGUES COMMUNICATIVE

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TRADITIONAL METHODS VERSUS COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING METHOD

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Abstract

L'article examine et compare les traits caractéristiques des méthodes traditionnelles et de la méthode d'enseignement communicatif des langues. Les avantages et les inconvénients ainsi que les caractéristiques de chaque méthode sont soulignés en détail. Les méthodes directes et de traduction grammaticale sont considérées comme les méthodes les plus anciennes, tandis que la méthode d'enseignement communicatif des langues est considérée comme un membre de la nouvelle génération de méthodes d'enseignement. Il a été révélé que le CLT est une méthode plus complète en termes de couverture de toutes les compétences linguistiques par rapport aux autres méthodes mentionnées dans l'article.

Abstract

The article scrutinizes and compares the characteristic features of traditional methods and the Communicative Language Teaching method. Advantages and disadvantages, as well as characteristic features of each method are emphasized in detail. The Direct and Grammar-translation methods are considered to be the oldest methods while the Communicative Language Teaching method is regarded as a member of new generation of teaching methods. It was revealed that the CLT is a more comprehensive method in terms of covering all language skills compared to other methods mentioned in the article.

Mots clés: Méthode directe, Méthode grammaire-traduction, Enseignement communicatif des langues, compétences linguistiques.

Keywords: Direct method, Grammar-translation method, Communicative Language Teaching, language skills.

Introduction

As obvious, traditional methods as the Direct method and Grammar-translation method have always been indispensable tools in effective language learning. Each method has its advantages and disadvantages in language learning process. Though the afore-mentioned methods are old, they are still being used by well-known methodologists in language learning. It means that they are still be considered to be the best methods though they are old. To be old does not mean that they have already fallen out of use.

Currently, millions of people learn English by watching movies or show programs with subtitles or without subtitles. To develop pronunciation and speak like a native-speakers, millions of learners subscribe Netflix and other platforms. Watching TV series and follow the plot could be effective to boost the language input effectively. In this way, language learners enlarge their word-stock unceasingly. However, the meaning of some acquired words still remain obscure to the learners who learn the language via the Direct method. Be-

sides, the grammar rules are not focused on or mentioned superficially. For example, Specific names of some animals and plants are learnt generally.

Main part

Grammar rules are not explained in detail and only some nuances are emphasized without clarification. This method is more effective in developing pronunciation. Let's not forget that we learn our native language from birth to death via this method. While learning a foreign language, we never use our mother tongue. Language learning occurs without the usage of native language. Babayev Javid underlines this feature in his article: "Another method which neglects the usage of native language is the Direct method. When you watch any film with subtitles on the Youtube or Netflix, you unknowingly learn the language with the Direct method with its natural pronunciation, grammar and lexicology. There is usually no feedback here" [2, p.51].

The Direct method possesses a number of merits as follows;

a) authentic materials are used during the learning process.

- b) pronunciation skills are developed efficiently and learners speak like native speakers.
- c) the learners can enlarge their word stock consistently.
- d) there is no need to use a lot of resources.
- e) it is full of activities which makes it more exciting and interesting.
- f) it improves to develop language sense.
- g) it establishes a direct bond between contexts.
- h) it develops listening and speaking skills.

The Direct method has some demerits:

- a) it is less effective while learning the language at older ages.
- b) the meanings of some concepts remain obscure while enlarging word stock because of avoidance of using the mother tongue. It restricts the scope of vocabulary. All the words are not linked to their meanings.
- c) grammar details are not focused on profoundly and grammar is not taught systematically.
- d) as the grammatical and lexical errors are not accepted as strict mistakes, they make bad habits in learners.
- e) it is a teacher-centered method.
- f) there is less focus on writing and reading.

Cristopher Candlin and Henry Widdowson noticed that the Direct method of language learning was ineffective in classrooms. They saw a need for students to develop communicative skill and functional competence in addition to mastering language structures [4,p. 84].

Unlike the Direct method, Grammar-translation method is more effective in terms of understanding complex grammatical structures and the meanings of most specific terms. Native language is used while learning the language through this method which facilitates to perceive the imagery and some obscure unexplainable terms. The fact is that GTM is still being used by many language teachers at the lesson. Even ancient Greek and Latin were taught through this method in ancient times. As known from its name, this method is based on translation from the target to native language or vice-versa. Even the meanings of some specific words can be understood and comprehended by the learners. This allows the learner to acquire the language profoundly. The author notes in his article about the GTM: "Though its application dates back to ancient times, it is still being used by many teachers. The teachers who use this method at the lesson predominate while teaching English as a foreign language or as a second language" [3.p.49].

Grammar-translation method has some advantages which have been enumerated below;

1. It mainly focuses on developing reading, speaking and writing skills.
2. Both languages are studied comparatively grammatically and lexically which urges the learner to understand the language structure.
3. Errors are avoided.
4. Comprehension level can easily be checked via this method.
5. Language is taught from simple to complex.
6. Middle and low level students can learn the language more easily through this method.

7. This method can be applied in large classes.
 8. The teacher may use very few teaching materials during the lesson.
 9. Concepts become clearer
 10. Learners feel more relaxed while learning the language through this method due to the usage of mother tongue. Since they are not afraid of not being able to understand some concepts in native language.
- Along with advantages, GTM also has some disadvantages;

1. There is no much focus on listening skill.
2. The students go into details of grammar which are needless.
3. The lesson is teacher-centered.
4. The learners are unable to develop critical and logical thinking.
5. It does not prioritize the correct pronunciation.

Communicative language teaching requires a feedback which differs it from other methods. First of all, it should be noted that the lessons can be conducted on the basis of learner-centered method successfully. CLT has become a leading method in education institutions lately in terms of language learning. The main aim of this method is to provide communication. When a learner keeps in touch with another student remotely via Skype or any other social platforms, there is a communication between them. They interrogate with each other, share their views about something. In the meanwhile they provide feedback, as well. Despite the mistakes that the learners make in the process of language learning, this method is still considered to be one of the most effective methods compared to other traditional methods. Because Communicative language teaching method is more ideal in terms of coverage of all four language skills. CLT is very effective in teaching all language skills including reading, writing, speaking and listening. However, writing skill is developed on the basis of colloquial speech. These two major productive skills don't cover academic layer. For example, when the learner writes "I got goosebumps" or "LOL" on the Skype as a reaction of another language learner, they both learn colloquial layer of the language. To learn the structure of writing an academic essay is not fulfilled while learning the language through this method. Babayev Javid mentions this drawback in his article: "Chatting to some native-speakers is also helpful for a language learner. In this way, the students develop writing skill. But it doesn't mean that chatting to people on different kinds of networks definitely develops academic writing skill. This develops everyday colloquial speech that is full of jargons, argots, phrases, idioms and lots of abbreviations" [1, p.14]. Teaching reading skill is not so effective while learning the language through this method.

Chatting to native speakers online helps develop listening and speaking skills. However, academic layer of developing speaking skill is not encompassed effectively. Mainly, simple everyday vocabulary is used in the speech. But it depends on which person you communicate with on the social platform. A learner can learn even academic language via communication, though the likelihood of such learning is very weak.

Communicative language learning has some merits and demerits while learning a language. Considering above-mentioned characteristics, CLT has the following advantages;

1. CLT covers all four language skills in learning process.
2. There is feedback between the learner and teacher which facilitates to develop language input and operational function.
3. This method is entertaining and engages the teacher and student.
4. The learner develops the listening skill effectively and as a result he/she is able to speak like a native speaker.

Despite the advantages, it also has some disadvantages in language learning process;

1. Academic writing is not developed properly. Writing skill covers only colloquial layer.
2. There is not much focus on development of reading skill.
3. Mistakes that are made in the speech are not prioritized in learning process. The mistakes are accepted as a normal case.

Conclusion

Consequently, it is possible to underline that Communicative Language Teaching method seems to be

more effective in language learning compared to traditional methods of teaching a language. Since the CLT applies and covers all four language skills in learning process. Besides, the application of this method in teaching and learning process is not so boring, on the contrary, it is more entertaining.

References

1. Babayev Javid. Analysis of the CLT in terms of coverage of language skills. Publisher.agency: Proceedings of the 2nd International Scientific Conference «Academics and Science Reviews Materials» (March 9-10,2023). Helsinki, Finland,2023. 258.
2. Babayev Javid. The methods ignoring the usage of mother tongue. I international scientific conference. "World Science: achievements and innovations". Lviv. Ukraine. 27-28.10.2022. 92 p.
3. Babayev Javid. Characteristic features of Grammar-translation method. V International Scientific and Practical Conference «Modern science: theoretical and practical view», May 09-10, 2023, Madrid. Spain.60 p.
4. Richards, Jack; Rodgers, Theodore (2014). Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching(3rd ed.). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. pp. 23–24, 84–85